

ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE OF ISOLATED CULTURES IN CHILDREN WITH PURULENT-INFLAMMATORY DISEASES

A.Y. Islomov¹

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute¹

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15088569>

Abstract. *This article is devoted to the identification of etiologically significant pathogens of purulent-inflammatory diseases in children and the determination of their antibiotic resistance to cephalosporins and other antibiotics.*

Keywords: *purulent-inflammatory diseases, osteomyelitis, opportunistic pathogens, β -lactam, surgical, cephalosporins.*

Relevance. Recent data published in domestic and international literature indicate significant shifts in the etiology of purulent-inflammatory diseases, particularly a growing prevalence of opportunistic bacteria, with an expanding spectrum of microorganisms being recognized as pathogens [2,4,8]. The most common causative agents include Staphylococci, Escherichia coli, Streptococci, Gonococci, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, among others, often in symbiosis with anaerobic microorganisms [12,14,13,15]. Acute haematogenous osteomyelitis (AHO) is one of the destructive inflammatory bone diseases. AHO is characterized by the spread of a bacterial infection via the bloodstream into bone tissue. This condition primarily affects children, with boys being more commonly affected across all age groups. Symptoms progress rapidly, and complications can often lead to disability.

The most prominent and consistent symptom of AHO is bone pain, which is persistent and varies in intensity. A distinguishing feature is that the pain remains constant. Accurately determining the localization of the affected area is crucial for timely diagnosis.

A significant challenge in diagnosing osteomyelitis is that radiographic visualization of bone changes becomes possible only after a considerable delay due to the nature of the infection's progression. This often leads to diagnostic errors and delayed treatment. Therefore, the issue of late osteomyelitis diagnosis remains a significant clinical concern. This review aims to examine diagnostic methods for acute haematogenous osteomyelitis (AHO) and address the issue of delayed diagnosis in clinical practice [12,10,15].

Nowadays, modern medicine is unimaginable without antibiotics, which have significantly expanded treatment options for various diseases. However, their widespread and often uncontrolled use in clinical practice poses a significant global public health challenge.

Microorganisms with multidrug resistance (MDR) to antibacterial agents are of particular clinical concern. In hospital settings, multidrug-resistant Gram-negative bacteria such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Acinetobacter* spp. represent a major threat to hospitalized patients [15,17].

Respiratory tract infections are a pressing issue in modern healthcare. According to the World Health Organization, respiratory diseases rank first among all causes of morbidity and are among the top ten causes of death worldwide. Approximately 44% of these cases are attributed to infectious diseases of the upper respiratory tract (URT) and ear infections.

Inflammatory diseases of the upper respiratory tract involve pathological changes in the mucous membrane of the respiratory tract, extending from the nasal cavity to the tracheobronchial tree, while excluding the alveoli and bronchioles.

Interest in this issue is further justified by the widespread prevalence of respiratory diseases across all age groups. Respiratory conditions account for 27.6% of cases in adults, 39.9% in adolescents, and 61% in children [14,15].

The spread of microbial resistance to the majority of etiotropic drugs remains an intractable medical and social problem worldwide. The results of international studies show that resistance of pathogens to drugs causes up to 700 thousand deaths from infectious diseases per year, and by 2050 this figure may reach 10 million. The growth of resistance to antimicrobial drugs is noted both among out-of-hospital and hospital infections.

Bacteria entering the wound begin to show their vital activity and multiply in it on average after 6-12 hours. Therefore, tracking the species composition and establishing the dominant species of microorganisms in the structure of purulent-inflammatory diseases in humans continues to be an urgent public health problem [3,6,8]. *M. catarrhalis* is a gram-negative aerobic diplococcus, the frequency of production of β -lactamases by this bacterium is quite high, which predetermines the low efficacy of using unprotected penicillins in its relation; however, 100% sensitivity of almost all strains of this pathogen remains to amoxicillin/clavulanate.

The microbial spectrum of the human urinary tract undergoes qualitative and quantitative changes under the influence of various factors, the most significant of which include the use of chemotherapeutic antimicrobial agents and other pharmacological substances, urodynamic disorders, changes in the ecological environment, and various social determinants [16,17].

Chronic osteomyelitis is a global public health, medical, and economic issue, accounting for up to 10% of all musculoskeletal disorders. Osteomyelitis treatment is typically complex, prolonged, and involves multiple stages, often with frequent relapses [13,15].

The necessity of rational and adequate etiotropic treatment for patients with respiratory tract infections is unquestionable. In actual clinical practice, antimicrobial therapy at the initial stage is prescribed empirically, targeting the complete eradication of the most likely pathogens [12,14].

Summary: Factors contributing to their development include:

- a) The presence of a nutrient-rich environment in the injury site (hemorrhage, necrotic tissues);
- b) The simultaneous presence of multiple microbial species (polymicrobial infection);
- c) Introduction of highly virulent microbes, for example, contamination of the injury site with purulent discharge from another patient;
- d) Weakness of immunobiological responses;
- e) Impairment of both local and systemic blood circulation in the patient.

The most important aspect of this issue is the significant resistance of pathogens to antimicrobial agents, including the latest antibiotics [1,2,5,7,9,10,11,17].

Aim of the study. To identify etiologically significant pathogens of acute purulent-inflammatory (API) infections in children and to determine their antibiotic resistance to cephalosporins and other antibiotics.

Study methods. To determine antibiotic resistance, the disc diffusion method was used [5]. Mueller-Hinton medium (HIMEDIA, India) was used as the nutrient medium; for fastidious

microorganisms, 5% blood was added to the medium. Commercial antibiotic discs (HIMEDIA, India and Russia) from the following groups were used: cephalosporins - I generation - cefazolin, II generation - cefuroxime, III generation - ceftazidime, cefotaxime, ceftriaxone, cefoperazone and IV generation - cefepime.

Results and Discussion. The sensitivity of bacteria isolated from pathological material taken from 120 children with acute haematogenous osteomyelitis and soft tissue infections undergoing inpatient treatment was studied. A total of 290 strains of microorganisms were isolated from pus, blood, bone tissue aspirates, and intraoperative material.

Among the etiological agents, Gram-positive cocci predominated, with 195 strains identified, including coagulase-positive (CPS) and coagulase-negative staphylococci (CNS), accounting for 67.2% of all isolates. Opportunistic Enterobacteriaceae and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* accounted for 19.7% (57 strains) and 13.1% (38 strains), respectively.

The antibiotic susceptibility of the isolated cultures was determined using the disc diffusion method on nutrient medium, according to the criteria of the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI, formerly NCCLS). The interpretation of inhibition zone diameters was performed according to CLSI guidelines, in accordance with the Performance Standards for Antimicrobial Disk Susceptibility Tests, CLSI (2007).

When analysing the distribution of strains by sensitivity to cephalosporin antibiotics, the tested drugs were divided into 5 groups: with a very high frequency of sensitive or resistant strains (more than 80%), high (61-80%), medium (41-60%), moderate (21-40%) and low (up to 20%).

The results of determining the sensitivity to cephalosporins of *S. aureus* strains isolated from children with surgical infection show a very high frequency of antibiotic-resistant variants (Table 1).

Susceptibility of *S. aureus* strains isolated from children with surgical infections to cephalosporins.

Table №1

Antibiotics	Distribution of strains by level of resistance (%)		
	Sensitive	Intermediate	Resilient
Cefazolin	80.3±3.3	0.7±0.7	19.0±3.2
Cefoperazone	66.0±3.9	19.0±3.2	15.0±3.0
Cefuroxime	60.5±4.1	17.7±3.1	21.8±3.6
Cefotaxime	61.9±4.0	17.0±3.1	21.1±3.4
Cefoxitin	68.0±4.7	1.0±0.9	31.0±4.6
Ceftriaxone	67.0±4.7	0	33.0±4.7
Ceftazidime	65.0±4.8	7.0±2.6	28.0±4.5
Cefepime	64.0±4.8	3.0±1.7	33.0±4.7

The frequency of detection of resistant bacterial variants to cefuroxime was characterized as moderate. On the contrary, sensitive staphylococcal variants were identified with a very high frequency to cefazolin and with a high frequency to cefoperazone, cefotaxime, cefoxitin, ceftriaxone, ceftazidime, and cefepime. These drugs should be considered drugs of choice for empirical antibiotic therapy of purulent surgical infections in children with staphylococcal etiology.

Analysis of the distribution of opportunistic Enterobacteriaceae strains by antibiotic susceptibility levels showed that resistant variants were isolated with very high or high frequency

(Table 2). Susceptibility of Enterobacteriaceae spp. strains isolated from children with surgical infections to cephalosporins.

Table № 2

Antibiotics	Distribution of strains by level of resistance (%)		
	Sensitive -S	Intermediate -I	Resilient -R
Cefazolin	21.4±6.3	0	78.6±6.3
Cefoperazone	35.7±1.4	11.9±5.0	52.4±7.0
Cefuroxime	19.0±6.0	0	81.0±6.0
Cefotaxime	16.6±5.7	4.8±3.3	78.6±6.3
Cefoxitin	34.1±7.1	2.3±2.3	63.6±7.3
Ceftriaxone	50.0±7.5	6.8±3.8	43.2±7.5
Ceftazidime	47.7±7.5	6.8±3.8	45.5±7.5
Cefepime	52.3±7.5	0	47.7±7.5

Thus, a very high frequency of detection of resistant Enterobacteriaceae variants was established for cefuroxime, and a high frequency for cefazolin, cefotaxime, and cefoxitin. These drugs should not be used in empirical antibiotic therapy for acute surgical infections in children caused by Enterobacteriaceae.

Sensitive variants of Enterobacteriaceae were isolated with high frequency only for cefepime and ceftriaxone. These drugs are considered the drugs of choice for the empirical prescription of antibiotics in surgical infections in children of enterobacterial etiology. The choice of other drugs should be based on the results of laboratory susceptibility testing of Enterobacteriaceae to antibiotics.

Even higher rates of antibiotic resistance were observed in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strains isolated from children with acute surgical infections (Table 3).

Susceptibility of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strains isolated from children with surgical infections to cephalosporins

Table № 3

Antibiotics	Distribution of strains by level of resistance (%)		
	Sensitive -S	Intermediate -I	Resilient -R
Cefazolin	0	0	100.0
Cefoperazone	6.5±4.4	3.2±3.2	90.3±5.3
Cefuroxime	3.2±3.2	0	96.8±3.2
Cefotaxime	3.2±3.2	0	96.8±3.2
Cefoxitin	0	0	100.0
Ceftriaxone	0	0	100.0
Ceftazidime	16.7±5.0	0	83.3±5.0
Cefepime	16.7±5.0	0	83.3±5.0

All studied cephalosporins (cefazolin, cefoperazone, cefuroxime, cefotaxime, cefoxitin, ceftriaxone, ceftazidime, cefepime) demonstrated a very high frequency of resistant *Pseudomonas* strains. Thus, among the strains isolated from children with osteomyelitis and soft tissue infections, on average, *S. aureus* exhibited susceptibility (S) in 67% of cases, intermediate susceptibility (I) in 8%, and resistance (R) in 25%. In contrast, among opportunistic Enterobacteriaceae, 35% were susceptible (S), while 61% were resistant (R) to the tested antibiotics. All *P. aeruginosa* strains were highly resistant (94%) to all tested antibiotics. For the selection of other antibiotics,

preliminary susceptibility testing of *P. aeruginosa* strains isolated from children with surgical infections should be performed.

Conclusions:

It was found that the susceptibility of surgical infection pathogens in children to cephalosporin antibiotics depends on the bacterial species and the type of antibiotic.

It has been established that Enterobacteriaceae and *Pseudomonas* strains isolated from children with surgical infections exhibited very high (over 80%) and high (63–80%) resistance rates to cefuroxime, cefazolin, and cefotaxime. Additionally, *Pseudomonas* strains also demonstrated resistance to cefoperazone. These antibiotics should not be used for empirical antibiotic therapy in children with surgical infections.

It has been demonstrated that susceptible bacterial variants were detected with very high or high frequency among staphylococci for cefazolin, cefuroxime, cefotaxime, ceftazidime, and cefepime. The selection of other antibiotics should be based on the results of laboratory susceptibility testing of the pathogens.

REFERENCES

1. V.A. Ageevets, I.V. Partina, E.S. Lisitsyna. Sensitivity of gram-negative bacteria producing carbapenemases to antibiotics of various groups. *Antibiotics and Chemotherapy*. 2013, Vol. 58, No. 3-4, pp. 10-13.
2. N.G. Berdnikova, O.Yu. Klimova, D.V. Tsyganko, et al. Some aspects of bacterial infections of the upper respiratory tract: what remains behind the scenes of clinical guidelines? *Medical Council*. 2017; 11: 64-70.
3. N.M. Belokryloe, A.V. Shchepalov, D.V. Antonov, A.N. Belokryloe, E.A. Zhuzhgov. On the issue of osteomyelitis and its consequences in children. *Perm Medical Journal*. 2020, Vol. XXXVII, No. 3, pp. 40-57.
4. M.Yu. Kabanov, M.A. Binienko, M.Ya. Belikova, K.V. Sementsov. Treatment of postoperative anterior mediastinitis and sternal osteomyelitis in a patient with a new coronavirus infection (COVID-19). *Surgery. Journal named after N.I. Pirogov*. 2021, No. 4, pp. 53-57.
5. R.S. Kozlov. Antibiotic resistance as one of the main problems of modern healthcare. *Bulletin of Roszdravnadzor*. 2017; 4: 28-33.
6. M.I. Kogan, V.L. Medvedev, Yu.L. Naboka, D.V. Sizyakin, S.N. Ivanov, G.A. Palaguta, I.A. Gudima. Antibiotic resistance of microorganisms isolated from urine of patients before surgical treatment of benign prostatic hyperplasia: data from a 7-year multicenter study. *Bulletin of Urology*. 2024; 12(2): 23-32.
7. S.A. Markosyan, A.P. Vlasov, S.A. Charyshkin. Antibacterial therapy for secondary peritonitis in different age groups. *EXIMIAE. Acta named after N.I. Pirogov*. 2022, No. XII, pp. 85-91.
8. T. Omurbekov, U. Mirzaev, D. Miklukhina. Modern concepts of diagnosis and treatment of acute hematogenous osteomyelitis in children. *EJH* 2024, 5, pp. 100-109.
9. O.A. Noskova, E.D. Sevilov, N.N. Chemezova, N.L. Belkova. Antibiotic resistance of pathogens of generalized purulent-septic infections in children. *Epidemiology and Vaccine Prevention*. 2020; 19(6): 56-61.

10. N.E. Paiganova, A.P. Yastremsky. Prospects for the use of antimicrobial peptides in otorhinolaryngology in the context of increasing antibiotic resistance. *Bulletin of Otorhinolaryngology*. 2021, Vol. 86, No. 3, pp. 104-109.
11. V.M. Svistushkin, G.N. Nikiforova, P.S. Artamonova. Antibacterial therapy of ENT diseases during the COVID-19 pandemic. / *Consilium Medicum*. 2020; 22 (11): 10-15.
12. V.M. Svistushkin, G.N. Nikiforova, P.S. Artamonova. Antibacterial therapy of ENT diseases during the COVID-19 pandemic. / *Consilium Medicum*. 2020; 22 (11): 10-15.
13. P .O. Shkelyaev, I.I. Yagudin, D.K. Karakulina, U.V. Belokrylova. The problem of late diagnosis of acute hematogenous osteomyelitis in children. *Vyatsky Medical Bulletin*, No. 2 (82), 2024, pp. 80-84.
14. Yu.S. Svetlichnaya, E.N. Kolosovskaya, L.A. Kaftyreva. Microbiological monitoring in the epidemiological surveillance system for nosocomial infections. *Epidemiology and Vaccine Prevention*. 2014, No. 1(74), pp. 9-14.
15. V.M. Svistushkin, G.N. Nikiforova, P.S. Artamonova. Antibacterial therapy of ENT diseases during the COVID-19 pandemic. / *Consilium Medicum*. 2020; 22 (11): 10-15.
16. I.V. Shipitsyna, E.V. Osipova. The role of anaerobic microflora in the etiology of chronic osteomyelitis. *Clinical Laboratory Diagnostics*. 2024; 69 (2): 92-96.
17. A.S. Sudnitsyn, A.L. Shastov, N.M. Klyushin, G.Kh. Rashidov. First experience of using a partially bioresorbable bone replacement material in a patient with chronic tibial osteomyelitis of 34 years' duration. *Orthopedic Genius*. 2025; 31(1): 60-65.